

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: WENAREEBA****FIRST NAME: NAME MORRIS****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 11%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2024 on Windows 11

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D PERIOD 6

1. What is the primary purpose of academic essay writing, as discussed in the *ACA-401*

Coursepack?

- To entertain readers with fictional narratives.
- To provide answers based on evidence to define hypotheses.¹**
- To persuade readers to adopt a particular viewpoint.
- To summarize general knowledge on a topic.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 5th ed. (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 7.

2. According to the Turabian style, how should a book be cited in the bibliography using the notes-bibliography style?

Author's last name, first name. Title. Edition. City: Publisher, Year.²

Title. Author's last name, first name. Edition. City: Publisher, Year.

Author's first name, last name. Title. Edition. City: Publisher, Year.

Title. Author's first name, last name. Edition. City: Publisher, Year.

3. What is the recommended sequence for completing a dissertation as described in *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*?

Research design, data collection, literature review, and conclusion.

Concept paper, prospectus, dissertation, and manuscript³

Introduction, findings, analysis, and literature review.

Literature review, methodology, abstract, and defense.

4. What is the role of triangulation in qualitative research according to *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*?

To ensure the validity and reliability of data through multiple perspectives.⁴

To reduce the sample size required for the study.

To improve the speed of data collection.

² Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 9th ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press., 2018), 149.

³ James P. Sampson Jr., *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 5.

⁴ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap From Beginning to End*, 4th ed. (Los Angeles: Sage, 2019), 478.

- To focus exclusively on one type of data source.
5. What is the purpose of a literature review in dissertation research, according to *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*?
- To summarize the historical evolution of a research topic.
- To critically analyze existing studies and identify research gaps.**⁵
- To provide statistical evidence for the research hypotheses.
- To describe the methodology in detail.
6. What is the primary recommendation for quoting text in the European Commission English Style Guide?
- Use quotation marks only for direct speech.
- Consistently reproduce the original text with quotation marks or italics.**⁶
- Rephrase the original text to match the document's tone.
- Avoid using quotation marks in official texts.
7. According to the *European Commission English Style Guide*, when should the -is form be used instead of -iz?
- Only when referring to British institutions.
- To maintain consistency in EU texts as a general rule.**⁷

⁵ Ibid., 352-353.

⁶ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. 8th ed. (Brussels: European Commission, 2021), 7.

⁷ Ibid., 7.

- For all technical and scientific terms.
 - Exclusively for American publications.
8. In what way does the conceptual framework support qualitative dissertations?
- It establishes how statistically significant the results are.
 - It provides a framework for the organization and interpretation of data.⁸**
 - It replaces theoretical frameworks.
 - It describes data collection procedures.
9. How should a research problem be articulated in qualitative research?
- It must be concise, actionable, and significant to stakeholders.⁹**
 - It should focus on broad and general societal challenges.
 - It needs to avoid alignment with theoretical frameworks.
 - It must only concern demographic trends.
10. According to the *ACA-401 Coursepack*, which of the following scenarios is an example of plagiarism?
- Copy a paragraph verbatim from a source and enclose it in quotation marks with a citation.
 - Paraphrase an author's idea in your own words and include a citation to the source.

⁸ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map From Beginning to End*, 4th ed. (Los Angeles: Sage, 2019), 268.

⁹ *Ibid.*, 182.

- Using a statistic from a study without citing the source, assuming it is common knowledge.
- Incorporating a unique idea from another source without crediting the original author¹⁰**

¹⁰ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepark: Period 1*, 5th ed. (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 34.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.